

MODEL EVALUATION & BENCHMARKING

Community survey summary report

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objective & format of the survey

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) serves a wide range of communities, all with their own specialized model evaluation & benchmarking needs, as well as associated data requirements for both observations and models. This survey aimed to identify how the CMIP community engaged in model evaluation for CMIP6 and other CMIP generations, and to explore ways in which these model analyses could be better facilitated in the future.

In particular, the survey targeted 3 areas:

- 1) How did respondents engage with CMIP?
- 2) What was their satisfaction with CMIP models & observations?
- 3) What are their aspirations for model attributes & benchmarking.

The full survey form can be found in [Annex A](#).

1.2 Survey Design Process

In spring 2024, Fresh Eyes on CMIP (FEoC) Model Evaluation subgroup members created the following CMIP community survey on Model Evaluation & Benchmarking. The vision and content of this survey were designed in collaboration with the Model Benchmarking CMIP Task Team, in order to meet several needs for the Task Team's planned work (see 3. Next Steps for details).

1.3 Target audience & distribution

This survey was targeted at members of the CMIP-related community who download, read, and analyze CMIP data for model evaluation and benchmarking. The survey was distributed by the CMIP IPO to the CMIP community mailing list, FEoC mailing list, and other relevant lists, with encouragement to share the survey more widely with colleagues (there were no restrictions on respondents). The survey was open to respondents for almost two weeks between 7th May and 17th May 2024.

2 Profile of Respondents

There were 152 unique survey responses. The profile of respondents is summarized below, with asterisks (*) denoting questions that allowed the selection of multiple answers.

- **Role(s) in CMIP* (Fig. 1a):** Majority (over 100 respondents) were involved in CMIP Output Analysis. A large number of respondents were involved in Modelling Groups or Centres, or Fresh Eyes on CMIP.
- **Geography/CMIP Access Location (Fig. 1b):** Most respondents access CMIP data from Europe (~50%) and North America (~25%), with a smaller number of participants from Asia, Oceania, Africa, and South America.
- **Career Stage (Fig. 1c):** Almost half of respondents had seven or more years of experience post-graduation. The remaining respondents were split evenly between Graduate Students, 0–3 years postgrad, and 4–7 years postgrad.
- **Phase(s) of CMIP Engagement* (Fig. 1d):** CMIP6 was used by almost all respondents. Most respondents also used CMIP5, while CMIP6Plus and CMIP3 were used by a smaller, but significant, fraction of respondents.

Figure 1: Profile of Respondents

- **Area(s) of expertise* (Fig. 1e):** Most respondents were experts in Atmosphere and/or Earth Systems science. There were also respondents from all other areas defined in the survey, including almost half of respondents being experts in Ocean & Sea-ice science. Many respondents were experts in two or more areas.
- **CMIP Product(s) Used* (Fig. 1f):** ScenarioMIP was used by over two-thirds of respondents. Respondents also covered all other MIPs. At least 20 respondents engaged with each of HighResMIP, PMIP, CORDEX, DAMIP, C4MIP, and AerChemMIP. These MIP options were based on CMIP6, and some respondents also engaged with the following additional MIPs that are not included in the Figure 1: CMIP/DECK, FireMIP, ESM-SnowMIP, RAMIP, NASA NEX GGDP, PDRMIP, and AMIP.

These results collectively underscore the diverse engagement and expertise within the CMIP community, highlighting areas of strong involvement, but also potential gaps in regional representation and role diversity. The prevalence in the area of expertise towards Atmosphere, and also the strong usage of ScenarioMIP, might reveal a general bias of the CMIP Community itself or a bias in respondents of this survey. The career stage of the respondents points out the strong background and experience of this community which is reflected in the good quality and details of the answers (see ,3).

3 Survey Results

3.1 Satisfaction with CMIP Models & Observations

The first portion of the survey questions asked respondents to: (1) Select aspects of models & observations they have engaged with, (2) rate their satisfaction with each engaged-with aspect (1-star to 5-star scale), and (3) explain their satisfaction choice.

The survey revealed varied satisfaction levels among respondents regarding different aspects of the CMIP model and observation data.

3.1.1 Model Aspects

The satisfaction ratings for the **Model Data Format** indicate a high level of satisfaction, with most respondents giving it 5 stars, followed by a significant number rating it 4 stars. Only a small fraction rated it 3 stars or lower (Figure 2a). **Model Data Access, Model Metadata, and Model Evaluation Tools** had similar satisfaction rating distributions. Most respondents gave 4 stars, followed by 3 stars, then 5 stars, and finally a few 1- and 2-star ratings, indicating a generally positive reception but with room for improvement in all aspects. Note that significantly fewer respondents engaged with model evaluation tools compared to the other model rating categories. The largest group of **Model Documentation** ratings was 3 stars, followed closely by 2-star ratings, and a considerable number gave it only 1 star. This highlights a critical area needing attention to meet user needs more effectively.

Overall, Model Data Format is rated very highly, and ratings are also generally high for Model Data Access, Model Metadata, and Model Evaluation Tools (with some room for improved user experiences). However, Model Documentation ratings exhibit a range of satisfaction levels, underscoring a need to address user concerns to improve overall satisfaction.

Figure 2 Satisfaction ratings for CMIP models

3.1.2 Observation Aspects

Observation Data Format received predominantly positive feedback, with most respondents giving it 5 stars, indicating a high level of satisfaction, similar to its model counterpart.

For **Observation Metadata**, the most popular rating was 4-stars. However, many other respondents gave it 2- or 3-stars, and a few gave 1- or 5-stars, indicating room for improvement.

For **Observation Data Availability**, the most popular satisfaction rating was 3-stars and almost all respondents gave 3-, 4- or 5-stars suggesting widespread, but minor, dissatisfaction. For both **Observation Data Access** and **Observation Documentation**, most respondents provided 1-, 2-, or 3-star satisfaction ratings, with 3-stars the most popular rating, suggesting a significant dissatisfaction with these aspects.

Overall, the survey results indicate a high level of satisfaction with Observation Data Format, but they also highlight the need for improvements in Observation Data Access, Metadata, Documentation, and Data Availability, to better meet user expectations.

Figure 3 Satisfaction ratings for observation data

3.2 Aspirations for Model Attributes & Benchmarking

“What new attributes (if any) would you like to see included in future CMIP products?”

64 respondents provided an answer to this question. Recurring themes included:

- **Documentation & Metadata for All Models/Experiments:** Uniform and centralized documentation and metadata to ensure consistency and ease of access.
- **Derived Data:** Need for archived, traceable, and easy-to-access derived data, with regridding capabilities.
- **Data Homogeneity:** Suggestions included standardizing calendars, setting grid parameters, coordinate names, and time chunks to ensure data uniformity.
- **Errata Tracking:** Automated notification systems and easy version control were highlighted as important for managing errata effectively.
- **High-Resolution Data Availability:** There is a demand for temporal and spatial high-resolution data to enhance research and analysis.
- Tools to **Evaluate & Benchmark Climate-Impact Indices** or Model Scores/Performance
- **Improved Data Access:** Enhancements in data access platforms were recommended.
- **Impact-Focused and Human-Focused Benchmarks/Output:** Developing benchmarks and outputs focused on human impacts and implications.
- **Paleo-Data Benchmarking** to improve historical climate understanding.

“What is holding back the next generation of model benchmarking and evaluation?”

84 respondents provided an answer to this question. These answers can be grouped into data-related, evaluation/benchmarking tools & metrics, and other responses. Many of these responses overlap with ideas introduced in response to the previous question.

Data-related recurring themes:

- Need for **derived data** that is archived and traceable, increasing transparency and reliability in data lineage.
- Stringent **quality control** of data is needed to ensure data accuracy and usability.
- **Data homogeneity** emerged as a critical issue, with specific calls for standardization in calendars, regridding processes, coordinated naming conventions, and time chunking to

facilitate consistent and comparable data analysis. There is also a need for more formatted observations, which would allow for more efficient and accurate data usage.

- **Errata tracking** improvements, with respondents advocating for automated notifications and easy version control to manage corrections and updates efficiently.
- There is demand for **high-frequency & high-resolution output** access, which is crucial for detailed spatio-temporal analysis.
- **Synchronized & timely data releases.** The varying time that data becomes available across different models and experiments was highlighted as a hindrance.

Evaluation/Benchmarking Tools & Metrics recurring themes:

- **Evaluate & benchmark climate-impact indices** effectively, to provide relevant insights into the models' implications on climate impacts.
- The **introduction of a benchmarking "test mode"**, possibly utilizing multiple software tools, to ensure the correct data format is achieved pre-publication.
- **Acceptance of non-CMOR data**, potentially with AI-assisted reformatting, was proposed to enhance data inclusivity and flexibility.
- **Server-/ESGF-/cloud-based computing**, along with guidance, was emphasized as a means to improve computational resources and data processing capabilities.
- The development of a **single community analysis tool** was highlighted to streamline and unify the analysis process.
- **Paleodata benchmarking** was identified as a critical need, given the limited observations, MIP data, and lack of high-resolution paleo simulations, which are essential for historical climate analysis.

Other recurring themes:

- **Complete, centralized model documentation** was identified as a crucial requirement to ensure all relevant information is easily accessible and standardized.
- **Easily accessible model scores** for relevant metrics would enable users to quickly evaluate and compare model performance based on standardized criteria.
- The **lack of regional human resources** was noted as a significant challenge, driving regional benchmarking inequity. This suggests the need for more inclusive and geographically diverse participation in model benchmarking activities.

4 Next Steps

The author team has greatly appreciated the comprehensive feedback, insights, and suggestions provided by the survey respondents. Moving forward, the team will continue to analyze the survey data to identify areas for improvement and innovation. They will also explore how the survey results can be utilized in collaboration with other groups, such as CMIP Task Teams and Fresh Eyes on CMIP subgroups. These efforts will aim to enhance the quality and impact of CMIP products and processes, fostering greater engagement and collaboration within the climate modeling community.

Annex A – Model Evaluation Survey Form

The following is a Word version of the Airtable survey distributed to the CMIP community:

This survey is being sent to members of the CMIP community who download, read and analyze CMIP data for model evaluation and benchmarking. The purpose of this survey is to identify how the community engages in CMIP6 model evaluation, and to explore ways in which model evaluation could be better facilitated in the future. Feel free to share this survey with those you know involved in CMIP model evaluation.

About you

What is your general area of expertise?

Select all that apply

- Atmosphere
- Biogeochemistry
- Earth system
- Impacts & adaptation
- Land & land-ice
- Ocean & sea-ice
- Other (*free text box*)

What is your current career stage?

If you have had a career break due to caring or other reasons, please do not include this period of time in your answer.

- Undergraduate student
- Graduate (e.g., PhD, Masters) student
- 0-3 years after last Graduate degree
- 4-7 years after last Graduate degree
- 7+ years after last Graduate degree
- Other (*free text box*)

About your use of CMIP data

Which generation of CMIP models do you work with?

- CMIP3
- CMIP5
- CMIP6
- CMIP6Plus

[If CMIP6 was selected]

Have you ever directly accessed CMIP6 data?

- Yes
- No

[If Yes was selected]

In which region are/were you based when you last accessed CMIP6 data? *[single select]*

- Africa
- Antarctica
- Asia
- Europe
- North America
- Oceania
- South America

[If Yes was selected]

If you know which node(s) you accessed the data from, please select: *[multiple select]*

- ceda.ac.uk
- dkrz.de
- ipsl.upmc.fr
- llnl.gov
- nci.org.au
- Other *(please specify; free text box)*

How have you been involved with CMIP?

Select all that apply.

- CMIP6 forcing dataset provider
- CMIP output analysis
- CMIP Panel or Task Team member
- Fresh Eyes on CMIP member
- ESGF
- MIP chair / science steering committee
- Modelling group or centre
- Climate Service Centre/group

Which CMIP MIP(s) or products did you interact with?

Select all that apply, for pre-CMIP6 select closest equivalent MIP(s)

- AerChemMIP
- C4MIP
- CDRMIP
- CFMIP
- CORDEX
- DAMIP
- DCPD
- DynVarMIP
- FAFMIP
- GeoMIP
- GMMIP
- HighResMIP
- ISMIP6
- LS3MIP
- LUMIP
- Obs4MIPS
- OMIP
- PAMIP
- PMIP
- RFMIP
- ScenarioMIP
- SIMIP
- VIACS AB
- VolMIP
- Other (free text box)

Performing Model Evaluation Tasks

Which of the following have you encountered when performing model evaluation tasks?

Select all that you've had experience with using/accessing/including in your workflows

- Model data access
- Model data format (netCDF)
- Model metadata
- Model documentation
- Model evaluation tools
- Observational data availability (is there data available you can use)
- Observational data format
- Observational data access
- Observation metadata
- Observation documentation

Satisfaction Ratings

For everything you indicated you have encountered when performing model evaluation tasks, please rate how satisfied you were with each element.

For each selected box, a five-star rating scale is provided where:

- 1 star = very dissatisfied
- 2 stars = dissatisfied
- 3 stars = neutral
- 4 stars = satisfied
- 5 stars = very satisfied

[condition on each very dissatisfied or very satisfied]

Please explain your satisfaction choice

Free text box

Future Aspirations

What new attributes (if any) would you like to see included in future CMIP products?

Free text box

In your opinion, what is holding back the next generation of model evaluation and benchmarking?

Free text box